

Bathymetric distribution and aspects of the life history of the loliginid squid *Loligo vulgaris* (Mollusca: Cephalopoda) in the Catalan sea (NW Mediterranean)

Distribución batimétrica y aspectos del ciclo biológico del calamar *Loligo vulgaris* (Mollusca: Cephalopoda) en el mar Catalán (Mediterráneo NO)

Pilar SÁNCHEZ* and Ángel GUERRA**

ABSTRACT

Of the 263 trawl catches studied during 1991 carried out at depth between 12 m and 645 m in the Catalan sea, *Loligo vulgaris* appeared in 68, at depth between 17 and 180 m. Negative allometric growth was observed between mantle length and weight in both sexes. According with the seasonal bathymetric distribution of sizes, large animals (150-250 mm ML), maturing or mature were found in waters of less than 100 m depth throughout the year, but above all in autumn and winter; immature specimens (<150 mm ML) were present at all depths throughout the year. Two migratory movements were detected: small squid hatched near the coast displacing towards deep water, and large (maturing or mature) animals moving towards coastal waters to spawning.

RESUMEN

De 263 pescas de arrastre realizadas durante 1991 entre 12 y 645 m de profundidad en el mar Catalán, *Loligo vulgaris* fue capturado en 68 de los lances entre 17 y 180 m de profundidad. Se observó un crecimiento alométrico negativo entre el peso total y la longitud del manto en ambos sexos. Se detectó una distribución batimétrica estacional. Ejemplares grandes (150-250 mm LM), madurando o maduros, se encontraron a menos de 100 m de profundidad durante todo el año, pero sobre todo en otoño e invierno; los ejemplares pequeños (<150 mm LM) aparecieron en todas las profundidades durante todo el año. Se observaron dos desplazamientos: los calamares pequeños que nacen cerca de la costa se desplazan hacia mayor profundidad y los grandes se mueven hacia la costa para la puesta.

KEY WORDS: Cephalopods, *Loligo vulgaris*, bathymetric distribution, biology, NW Mediterranean.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Cefalópodos, *Loligo vulgaris*, distribución batimétrica, biología, Mediterráneo noroccidental.

*Instituto de Ciencias del Mar (CSIC), Paseo Joan de Borbó s/n, 08039 Barcelona, Spain.

**Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas (CSIC), Eduardo Cabello 6, 36208 Vigo, Spain.

Correspondence address: Pilar Sánchez, Instituto de Ciencias del Mar (CSIC), Paseo Joan de Borbó s/n, 08039 Barcelona, Spain.

INTRODUCTION

Loligo vulgaris is a nektobenthic species, rather dependent on the bottom during the spawning season but has a more pelagic behaviour when foraging (WORMS, 1983).

Except on the Algerian Shelf, where some individuals were caught at a depth up to 550 m (WORMS, 1983), *L. vulgaris* seems to live usually between 10 and 150 m, the optimal depth being 50 to 60 m (MANGOLD-WIRZ, 1963; BURUKOVSKI, GAEVSKAYA, DOMANEVSKI, NIGMATULLIN AND PANFILOV, 1979; GUERRA, 1982, 1984; BADDYR, 1988). Both vertical and horizontal migratory movements have been shown in this species (WORMS, 1983).

Very little information is available concerning the temperature and salinity ranges where this species inhabits. TINBERGEN AND VERWEY (1945) noted that *L. vulgaris* in the North Sea occurs in shallow waters only when the salinity rises above 30‰, suggesting a range of salinity tolerance of 30-36‰. This species also seems to prefer warm temperature. BADDYR (1988) noted that *L. vulgaris* in Agadir Bay (Morocco) occurs in shallow waters where surface temperature ranges from 11.3°C to 22.7°C. Temperature and salinity ranges in experimental conditions have been recorded as 13.3-26.0°C and 34.0-37.0‰, respectively (BOLETZKY, 1979; TURK, HANLON, BRADFORD AND YANG, 1986).

Some aspects of the biology of *L. vulgaris* have been previously studied in the western Mediterranean Sea by several authors, MANGOLD-WIRZ (1963), WORMS (1980, 1983) and NATSUKARI AND KOMINE (1992) among others.

The aim of the present study is to consider the relationship between size and depth distribution for *L. vulgaris* caught by the commercial fleet in the northwestern Mediterranean, to attempt to verify the possible occurrence of seasonal migrations and to provide data about some aspects of its life history.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

From February to December 1991, a total of 263 samples were examined

from landings taken by trawlers in nine ports on the Catalan coast (from the French border to the Ebro delta, Figure 1). The mesh size of the cod-end was 36-38 mm. The depth range sampled was 12-645 m. 24 tows were made with the cod-end covered by a 10 mm mesh size covering bag in order to collect the smaller individuals: 10 in winter, 9 in spring, 3 in summer and 2 in autumn. A record of sampling depths was obtained by an observer on board. All trawls were performed during day-time hours.

In order to determine the population structure of this species in the study area, a total of 2438 specimens were examined. Mantle length (ML), taken in mm, was measured directly on board. Sexes were not differentiated in these samplings.

These specimens were classified by season and depth strata. Spring: April to June; Summer: July to September; Autumn: October to December and Winter: January to March. The depth strata considered were: less than 50 metres, between 50 and 100 metres and deeper than 100 metres.

An additional number of individuals, 235 males and 225 females, were examined in the laboratory. For each one of them, the following data were obtained: mantle length (ML) in mm, total weight (TW) in grammes, eviscerate weight in grammes, sex and reproductive stage, weight of the gonad in grammes. Gonads were weighed on electronic scales with an accuracy of 0.01 g. The relationship between ML and TW was estimated for all specimens and for each sex separately, using the potential model.

Temperature and salinity data from each season and strata were obtained from SALAT, FONT AND CRUZADO (1978).

RESULTS

Distribution and population structure: *Loligo vulgaris* appeared in 68 out of the 263 trawl samples studied. The depth of occurrence ranged between 17 and 180 m. One hundred eighty other species of the macrofauna were caught along with

Figure 1. Chart showing the study zone with the main fishing ports of the Catalan coast (NW Mediterranean) which reported the monthly cephalopod catches of the fishing fleet.

Figura 1. Zona de estudio mostrando los principales puertos pesqueros de la costa catalana (Mediterráneo NO) que proporcionaron las capturas mensuales de cefalópodos de la flota pesquera.

L. vulgaris. Among these, 10 can be considered as habitual accompanying species of the squid, since they appeared in over 50% of the catches where *L. vulgaris* was present (Table I). The most frequently co-occurring species were the hake, *Merluccius merluccius* (85.3% of appearances), and the crab, *Liocarcinus depurator* (79.4%), which are species with a wide bathymetric distribution.

Table II shows the number of samples taken, the number of samples where *L. vulgaris* appeared, and the mean number and biomass of *L. vulgaris* by season and depth strata.

Figures 2-5 show the size (ML) frequency distributions of *L. vulgaris* by sea-

son and depth strata. In spring (Fig. 2, Table III), most of the specimens caught were small (20-50 mm ML), especially at depths of less than 100 m. A few medium and large specimens were caught in the shallowest depth stratum. In summer, the highest densities occurred at depths of between 50 to 100 m (Table II); in this depth stratum, both small and medium-large individual were found (Fig. 3, Table III); hardly any medium-large individual occurred in the shallowest depth stratum. In autumn individuals within the whole size range of the species were found at depths of less than 100 m (Fig. 4, Tables II and III), whereas only very small specimens lived

Table I. Habitual accompanying species of *Loligo vulgaris*. occ: percentage of the species occurrence in the 68 catches, where *L. vulgaris* were present; no x h⁻¹: number of individuals per hour; kg x h⁻¹: kg per hour; avg: average; std: standard deviation.

Tabla I. Especies acompañantes habituales de *Loligo vulgaris*. occ: porcentaje de presencias por especie en las 68 pescas donde se encontró *L. vulgaris*; no x h⁻¹: número de individuos por hora; kg x h⁻¹: kg por hora; avg: media; std: desviación típica.

Species	occ	no x h ⁻¹		kg x h ⁻¹	
		avg	std	avg	std
<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	85.3	452.1	721.9	7.6	11.6
<i>Liocarcinus depurator</i>	79.4	329.3	745.4	3.0	5.3
<i>Citharus linguatula</i>	73.5	48.8	82.9	1.1	1.3
<i>Alloteuthis media</i>	70.6	77.2	125.4	0.8	1.2
<i>Cepola rubescens</i>	64.7	18.8	26.0	0.7	1.3
<i>Eledone cirrhosa</i>	58.8	21.7	22.4	2.1	3.5
<i>Conger conger</i>	57.4	6.5	9.3	0.9	1.4
<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	52.9	371.8	781.6	2.8	6.7
<i>Squilla mantis</i>	52.9	126.0	192.1	2.3	3.6
<i>Trachinus draco</i>	51.5	10.0	11.2	0.7	0.7

Table II. Abundance by depth strata and season. N: number of samples taken. n: number of samples where *L. vulgaris* appeared; nce: number of tows with cod-end covered by a 10 mm mesh size where *L. vulgaris* appeared; kg/h: kg per hour.

Tabla II. Abundancia por estratos de profundidad y estación. N: número de muestras tomadas; n: número de muestras donde apareció *L. vulgaris*; nce: número de pescas realizadas con un copo de malla terminal de 10 mm en las que apareció *L. vulgaris*; kg/h: kg por hora.

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
<50	N= 14	N= 30	N= 34	N= 17
	n= 7	n= 4	n= 10	n= 8
	nce= 0	nce= 0	nce= 0	nce= 0
	kg/h= 0.40	kg/h= 0.13	kg/h= 1.99	kg/h= 0.48
50-100	N= 23	N= 31	N= 11	N= 10
	n= 6	n= 13	n= 5	n= 4
	nce= 7	nce= 0	nce= 0	nce= 0
	kg/h= 0.35	kg/h= 1.06	kg/h= 1.86	kg/h= 0.84
>100	N= 23	N= 29	N= 27	N= 14
	n= 1	n= 3	n= 4	n= 3
	nce= 0	nce= 2	nce= 1	nce= 0
	kg/h= 0.18	kg/h= 0.08	kg/h= 0.07	kg/h= 0.14

in waters deeper than 100 m, as was also the case in summer. In winter (Fig. 5, Table III), most large (>150 mm ML) and medium-sized specimens (80-140 mm

ML) occurred shallower than 100 m. Small specimens (<70 mm ML) appeared in all depth strata considered, but they were more abundant at less than 50 m.

Figure 2. Bathymetric distribution of sizes of *Loligo vulgaris* in spring, n: number of specimens. Trawl fishery.

Figura 2. Distribución batimétrica de tallas de *Loligo vulgaris* en primavera, n: número de especímenes. Arrastre.

Figure 3. Bathymetric distribution of sizes of *Loligo vulgaris* in summer, n: number of specimens. Trawl fishery.

Figura 3. Distribución batimétrica de tallas de *Loligo vulgaris* en verano, n: número de especímenes. Arrastre.

Figure 4. Bathymetric distribution of sizes of *Loligo vulgaris* in autumn, n: number of specimens. Trawl fishery.

Figura 4. Distribución batimétrica de tallas de *Loligo vulgaris* en otoño, n: número de especímenes. Arrastre.

Figure 5. Bathymetric distribution of sizes of *Loligo vulgaris* in winter, n: number of specimens. Trawl fishery.

Figura 5. Distribución batimétrica de tallas de *Loligo vulgaris* en invierno, n: número de especímenes. Arrastre.

Table III. Percentage of specimens per stratum, estimated from the total number caught during each season, for adults (>150 mm ML) and juveniles.

Tabla III. Porcentaje de especímenes por estrato, estimados del total capturado durante cada estación, para adultos (>150 mm ML) y juveniles.

depth (m)	adults (>150 mm ML)				no. total	%total
	spring	summer	autumn	winter		
<50	100	12.5	72.7	43.6	100	64.1
50-100	0	87.5	26.3	51.3	53	34
>100	0	0	1.0	5.1	3	1.9
no. total	10	8	99	39	156	100

depth (m)	juveniles (<150 mm ML)				no. total	%total
	spring	summer	autumn	winter		
<50	29.8	3.3	68.9	46.8	679	29.8
50-100	67.8	84.8	15.8	41.7	1353	59.3
>100	2.4	11.9	15.3	11.5	250	11
no. total	413	1017	557	295	2282	100

Table IV. Estimated parameters, a and b, of the size-weight relationship ($TW = a \times ML^b$) by sex. Vb: variance of the slope, b; r^2 : determination coefficient; n: number of specimens.

Tabla IV. Parámetros estimados, a y b, de la relación talla-peso ($TW = a \times ML^b$) por sexos. Vb: varianza de la pendiente, b; r^2 : coeficiente de determinación; n: número de especímenes.

	a	b	Vb	r^2	n
Females	0.000270	2.572	0.0468	0.98	225
Males	0.000658	2.372	0.0497	0.96	235
All specimens	0.000391	2.491	0.0246	0.97	460

Table V. Gonad weight expressed as percentage of total body weight in immature and mature male and female *Loligo vulgaris*. GW: average of the gonad weight percentage; STD: standard deviation; N: number of observations.

*Tabla V. Peso de la gónada expresado como porcentaje del peso corporal total en machos y hembras inmaduros y maduros de *Loligo vulgaris*. GW: media del porcentaje del peso gonadal; STD: desviación típica; N: número de especímenes.*

	Males		Females	
	Immatures	Matures	Immatures	Matures
GW	0.16	5.07	0.26	16.79
STD	0.06	0.51	0.03	2.60
N	28	42	27	36

Females

Males

□ Inmatures ■ Maturing ■ Matures

Figure 6. Seasonal percentage (%) of *Loligo vulgaris* females and males in each maturity stage from Catalonia (NW Mediterranean) in 1991.

Figura 6. Porcentaje estacional (%) de machos y hembras de *Loligo vulgaris* en cada estado de madurez en Cataluña (Mediterráneo NO) en 1991.

Biological aspects: Table IV shows the estimated parameters of the size-weight relationship for both male and female *L. vulgaris*. Negative allometric growth was observed between mantle length and weight in both sexes, since the slope (b) of the relationship was significantly smaller (t-test, $p < 0.001$) than 3 in both cases. A comparison between the estimated parameters for males and females showed that growth in weight differed significantly between the sexes (t-test, $p < 0.01$). The overall relationship (males + females) was also presented since population data taken on board could not often distinguish between sexes.

The gonad weight was calculated relative to total weight (Table V) to try to elucidate whether the increase in weight in the females could be due to the growth of the gonads or to other factors. In immature individuals, the percentage of total weight represented by the gonads was similar in both sexes. In individuals which have begun to mature or are mature, the difference was very marked. The results of two-samples test showed a significant differences between mature and immature females ($t = 32.92$, $p < 0.01$) and between mature and immature males ($t = 51.07$, $p < 0.01$). The difference between mature males and mature females was also significantly different ($t = 28.57$, $p < 0.01$).

Figure 6 shows the proportion of the different maturity stages by season in females and males. Mature specimens of both sexes were detected throughout the year, but the highest proportions were found in autumn-winter. Mature specimens were detected at sizes larger than 130 mm ML in males and 160 mm ML in females.

DISCUSSION

The size-weight relationships give a greater weight gain for females longer than 110 mm ML. TINBERGEN AND VERWEY (1945) found that for *Loligo vulgaris* in the North Sea, the growth rates of males and females were approximately the same until they reach 120 mm ML.

WORMS (1980), obtained similar results. The greatest weight observed at a similar size in females can be mainly attributable to the development of the gonads.

The size at which *Loligo vulgaris* become mature in the northwestern Mediterranean, averages 150 mm ML for males and 170 mm for females (WORMS, 1983), although the occasional 100 mm ML male starting to form spermatophores can be found (MANGOLD-WIRZ, 1963). In the present study, individuals over 150 mm ML have been considered as large and mature squid (WORMS, 1983; present results). These were caught mostly (64.1%) between 25 m and 50 m, which suggests a preference for these depths for spawning, although spawning can also occur in deeper waters (50-100 m; 34% of the mature individuals examined).

According to the seasonal bathymetric distribution of sizes, large (150-250 mm ML) maturing or mature individuals were found in waters of less than 100 m depth throughout the year, but especially in autumn and winter. Small immature specimens (<150 mm ML) were present at all depths throughout the year, in agreement with the occurrence of some adult mature individuals throughout the year. However, data suggest that the part of the population which has grown in waters between 50 to 100 m moves towards coastal waters in autumn and winter, probably to spawn. It also seems that a part of the population born in coastal waters moves to deeper waters to grow and mature. Thus, it appears that two migration patterns occur: small squids hatched near the coast move towards deeper water, and large (maturing or mature) animals move towards coastal waters.

The two migratory movements detected, as well as the spawning in coastal waters, are in agreement with the observations of WORMS (1983) in the Mediterranean, but in the present study, it appears that only a portion of the young population migrates. The lack of more information on the differential distribution of the sexes and stages of sexual maturity prevent us from concluding whether there is

segregation by sex at different depths, and whether males and females form different schools which asynchronously migrate, as it was deduced from observations by MANGOLD-WIRZ (1963) and WORMS (1983).

The fact that all the examined specimens were caught by trawling (which in this area is always done by day), and from the composition of the accompanying species (Table I), suggests that at least an important part of the population of *L. vulgaris* stays close of the bottom during daytime. Only two species of those which habitually co-occur with the squid can be considered as pelagic: the cephalopod *Alloteuthis media* and the anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus*. The latter species is often caught by trawlers during the day in the study area, when the schools disperse and stay close to the bottom. *L. vulgaris* probably shows a similar strategy.

The range of salinities in which *L. vulgaris* was caught in the northwestern Mediterranean was 37.655 to 38.159‰ (SALAT

ET AL., 1978), which is higher than that indicated by WORMS (1983) (between 30.0 and 36.0‰ based on observations of TINBERGEN AND VERWEY, 1945), the reason being that the salinity of the North Atlantic is lower than that of the Mediterranean. The temperature range at which *L. vulgaris* was caught in the northwestern Mediterranean (12.66-25°C, SALAT ET AL., 1978) is basically the same observed by BADDYR (1988) in Moroccan waters (11.3-22.7°C).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge Dra. Paloma Martín and Dr. P. Abelló for comments on the manuscript and the members of Mediterranean Population Dynamics Group of the Instituto de Ciencias del Mar de Barcelona (PDPM) for their collaboration on samplings. We wish also to thank Mrs. M^a Teresa Fernández for her technical assistance.

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Recibido el 28-V-1993
Aceptado el 18-IV-1994

Publicado en junio de 1995